

GROWTH AND YIELD PERFORMANCE OF VEGETATIVELY PROPAGATED CHERRY TOMATO VARIETIES AS INFLUENCED BY DIFFERENT MEDIA UNDER GREENHOUSE CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Greenhouse farming offers a sustainable crop production amidst climate variability. This study, conducted at DA-NMACLR, Dalwangan, Malaybalay City, used a factorial in Completely Randomized Design to evaluate vegetative propagation and the effects of different growing media on growth, yield, and cost-efficiency on different varieties of cherry tomatoes. Results showed that Machyo Red had superior nursery performance, while M₃ (50% garden soil, 30% compost, 20% sawdust) and M₄ (30% garden soil, 30% compost, 40% rice hull) improved plant height and stem thickness. In the greenhouse, KT Red attained the highest yield, and M₃ was identified as the most cost-effective growing medium.

Keywords: Greenhouse Farming, Cherry Tomatoes, Vegetative Propagation, Growing Media, Cost-Efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Climate change significantly challenges global food security, influencing crop yields through altered weather patterns, increased pest and disease pressures, and more frequent extreme weather events. As conventional open-field agriculture becomes increasingly vulnerable to these changes, innovative farming approaches are explored to provide stable, controlled environments for sustainable crop production. Greenhouse farming offers a promising adaptation strategy, allowing crops to be cultivated in controlled conditions that mitigate the adverse effects of climate change. This controlled environment enhances productivity and helps ensure food security by reducing the risks associated with unpredictable weather patterns. Cherry tomatoes (*Solanum lycopersicum* var. *cerasiforme*) are a unique variety known for their small size, sweet and juicy flavor, thin skin, and versatility in culinary applications (Thompson & Thompson, 2018). They are nutrient-dense, rich in vitamin C and lycopene, and provide moderate amounts of vitamins A and K, potassium, fiber, and folate, making them a valuable component of a balanced diet (Coyago-Cruz et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2022). These nutritional benefits contribute to their well-documented antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-atherogenic properties, which have been associated with a reduced risk of cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and other chronic health conditions (Campestrini et al., 2019; Friedman et al., 2021; Ramos-Bueno et al., 2017; Tilesi et al., 2021). As a result, the popularity of cherry tomatoes has risen significantly, driving a need for innovative production techniques to meet increasing consumer demand. In traditional tomato cultivation, seeds are the most common method of propagation. However, vegetative propagation has emerged as a promising approach for optimizing cherry tomato production. This method offers several advantages over

traditional seed-based propagation, including uniform plant characteristics, faster maturation, and enhanced productivity. Furthermore, the high cost of seeds in some regions adds another incentive for exploring alternative propagation methods (Waheed et al., 2015; Nkongho et al., 2023). Vegetative propagation can increase crop yields, improve plant uniformity, and produce more consistent fruit, particularly in controlled environments like greenhouses. Greenhouse farming offers a strategic advantage in mitigating the challenges posed by climate change, allowing for year-round cultivation in a stable environment. However, greenhouse agriculture's success and sustainability are contingent on optimizing various factors, including the choice of growing medium and the selection of appropriate plant varieties. As Khobragade et al. (1997) emphasized, growing media should possess optimal aeration, water-holding capacity, and the ability to supply adequate nutrition for healthy plant growth. Vendrame et al. (2005) further highlighted that the growing medium is critical in influencing plant growth parameters such as height, leaf number, and overall plant health. Despite the potential of vegetative propagation, there is limited research on how different growing media influence the growth and yield of cherry tomatoes in greenhouses. This study evaluates the growth performance and yield of various vegetatively propagated cherry tomato varieties under different growing media in greenhouse conditions. The research will also assess the cost-efficiency of each medium, providing valuable insights for optimizing sustainable cherry tomato production in response to climate challenges.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted from July to December 2024 in the Smart Greenhouse Facility of the Department of Agriculture- Northern Mindanao Agricultural Crops and Livestock Research Complex (DA-NMACLRRC) at Dalwangan, Malaybalay City with a latitude 8.2143423 and longitude 125.0342871 as shown in Figure 1. The study was laid out in factorial design in Completely Randomized Design (CRD). The factors tested were Factor A: 3 Korean varieties of cherry tomato (KT Red, Machyo Red and Red Joy) and Factor B: different growing media (M1_a 50% cocopeat + 50% perlite and M1_b 100% coco chips (currently used media for nursery and greenhouse); 60% sawdust + 40% garden soil; 50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust and 30% garden soil + 30% compost + 40% rice hull). The study was conducted in 3 replications. The three varieties of cherry tomatoes were planted in the greenhouse to obtain side shoots or cuttings for vegetative propagation. Good quality cherry tomato side shoots (6-inch side shoots) from each variety were selected and were planted in seedling trays with the sterilized media and drenched with a nutrient solution at 1.5 EC, gradually increased to 2.0 EC over 2-3 days until 25 days after planting (DAP). The seedlings were transplanted into the growing house and adequately cared for and maintained following the IPM, and nutrients were supplied based on the Korean technology introduced. Data were collected from the 10 representative samples. The data collected for all parameters measured were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Factorial in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). Means were compared using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) Test to determine statistical significance.

Figure 1: Smart Greenhouse at DA-NMACLRC, Dalwangan, Malaybalay City

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Analysis of Macro Nutrients of Media Used

The nutrient composition of the media (Table 1) varied significantly. M_{1a} (50% perlite + 50% cocopeat), with a total NPK of 4.67, is low in nutrients and suitable for seedling development but requires supplementation. M_{1b} (100% coco chips) had higher nitrogen (0.71%) but lacked sufficient phosphorus and potassium, giving it a total NPK of 1.66. M₂ (60% sawdust + 40% garden soil) had the lowest total NPK of 0.81, with poor nutrient retention, limiting plant growth. M₃ (50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust) had the best nutrient profile (total NPK of 2.06), making it ideal for growth. M₄ (30% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 40% rice hulls) showed the lowest potassium (0.03%) and total NPK (0.47), likely due to rice hulls diluting nutrient content. M₃ is the most balanced and nutrient-rich medium; others may need supplementation for optimal growth.

Table 1: Macro nutrients analysis (as received) of the growing media used in the experiment

MEDIA (as received)	Total N (%)	Total P (%)	Total K (%)	Total NPK (%)
M _{1a} - 50% perlite + 50% cocopeat (control nursery media)	0.11±0.01	0.05	3.69	4.67
M _{1b} - 100% coco chips (control growing media)	0.71	0.07	0.65	1.66
M ₂ - 60% sawdust + 40% garden soil	0.17	0.07	0.39	0.81
M ₃ - 50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust	0.62±0.03	0.27	0.68	2.06
M ₄ - 30% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 40%rice hull	0.22±0.01	0.10	0.02	0.47

b. Secondary and microelements analysis of the growing media used

The secondary and micronutrient analysis of the growing media (Table 2) reveals that all media exhibit high levels of calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), copper (Cu), and manganese (Mn). Specifically, Ca content ranged from 0.07% to 2.26%, Mg from 0.03% to 0.49%, Cu from 22.85 to 63.54 ppm, and Mn from 127 to 1,072 ppm. Additionally, M_{1a}, M₂, and M₄ contained sodium (Na) levels of 0.01, 0.54, and 0.21 cmolkg⁻¹, respectively, while M_{1b} had the highest Na concentration at 6.47 cmolkg⁻¹, followed by M₃ at 0.84 cmolkg⁻¹. Notably, M_{1b} recorded the lowest iron (Fe) content (*<2.52 ppm), while the other media contained significantly higher Fe levels, ranging from 2,447 to 44,846 ppm. Zinc (Zn) content was within the normal range for M_{1a}, M_{1b}, and M₄, with values of 9.86, 11, and 9.76 ppm, respectively, whereas M₂ and M₃ exhibited very high Zn concentrations of 72.90 and 160 ppm. According to Zhang et al. (2021), the normal ranges for these nutrients in soilless growing media for general crops are as follows: Ca (0.008–0.02%), Mg (0.003–0.01%), Na (0.69 cmolkg⁻¹), Fe (5–30 ppm), Cu (0.5–1.5 ppm), Mn (5–30 ppm), and Zn (5–30 ppm).

Table 2: Secondary and microelements analysis of the growing media used in the experiment

MEDIA	Ca (%)	Mg (%)	Na (cmolkg ⁻¹)	Fe (ppm)	Cu (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Zn (ppm)
M _{1a} - 50% perlite + 50% cocopeat (control nursery media)	0.07	0.03	*<0.01	21,467	23.65	603	9.86
M _{1b} - 100% coco chips (control growing media)	2.26	0.49	6.47	*<2.52	48.00	127	11
M ₂ - 60% sawdust + 40% garden soil	0.47	0.13	0.54	44,846	59.76	974	72.90
M ₃ - 50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust	0.76	0.26	0.84	41,241	63.54	1,072	160
M ₄ - 30% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 40%rice hull	0.59	0.07	0.21	2,447	22.85	195	9.76

*- method detection limit

c. Percent Survival Rate in the Nursery

At 15 days after planting (Table 3), Machyo Red and M₂ media exhibited a slightly lower survival rate of 99%, while all other varieties and media achieved a full 100% survival rate. Survival rates were high and showed no significant differences based on variety, media, or interaction.

d. Plant Height (cm) in the nursery

Plant height 15 days after planting (DAP) (Table 3) showed significant treatment differences. Machyo Red was the tallest (25.40 cm), followed by Red Joy (24.29 cm) and KT Red (23.69 cm), reflecting differences in nutrient utilization due to genetic makeup (Ddamulira et al., 2019). Among media, M₃ produced the tallest plants (28.56 cm), followed by M₂ (24.64 cm), while M₄ (21.89 cm) and M₁ (22.72 cm) were the shortest.

The superior height in M₃ was attributed to its high nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) content, as nitrogen promotes internode growth (Biswas et al., 2015), and phosphorus supports photosynthesis and respiration (Sagerv anshi et al., 2012).

e. Stem Diameter (cm) in the nursery

The data (Table 3) showed that variety had a significant effect, and media had a highly significant effect on stem diameter. Machyo Red had the most prominent stem diameter (0.35 cm), followed by KT Red and Red Joy (0.31 cm), consistent with findings by Uddin et al. (2015) that stem thickness varies among lines and Klepper et al. (1971) that stem diameter changes with tissue hydration. Among media, M₄ recorded the highest stem diameter, followed by M₁ (Control), with no significant difference. The superior performance of M₄ was attributed to its air-filled pore spaces (Barrett et al., 2016), which improve drainage, gas exchange, and root growth. M₁'s performance was likely due to its richer nutrient content, enhancing photosynthesis and increasing stored material, resulting in thicker stems.

f. Number of Leaves in the Nursery

The number of leaves in cherry tomatoes (Table 3) was not significantly influenced by variety, growing media, or their interaction. The average leaf counts for KT Red, Machyo Red, and Red Joy were 4.03, 4.18, and 4.16, respectively, with the lowest average leaf count observed in M₂ (3.91). These findings align with those of Purba et al. (2021), who reported that the combination of different growing media had no significant effect on the number of leaves.

Table 3: Growth parameters of vegetatively propagated cherry tomatoes in the Nursery at 15 DAP

Treatment	Survival Rate (%)	Plant Height (cm)	Stem Diameter (cm)	No. of Leaves
Varieties				
KT Red	100	23.69 b	0.31 b	4.03
Machyo Red	99	25.40 a	0.35 a	4.18
Red Joy	100	24.29 ab	0.31 b	4.16
Rooting Media				
M ₁ - 50% perlite + 50% cocopeat	100	22.72 c	0.34 a	4.22
M ₂ - 60% sawdust + 40% garden soil	99	24.64 b	0.31 b	3.91
M ₃ - 50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust	100	28.56 a	0.29 c	4.29
M ₄ -30% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 40%rice hull	100	21.89 c	0.35 a	4.06

Different letters represent significant statistical values at (p<0.05).

g. Percent Survival Rate in the Greenhouse at 15 DAT

The results (Table 4) indicate that KT Red and Red Joy achieved a 100% survival rate among the varieties, while Machyo Red while Machyo Red had a slightly lower rate of 98%. On the other hand, for the growing media, M₁ (100% coco chips), M₃ (50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust), and M₄ (30% garden soil + 30% commercial compost +

40% rice hull) all resulted in a 100% survival rate. M₂ (60% sawdust + 40% garden soil) had a survival rate of 99%. Overall, both the variety and growing media had no significant effect on the seedling survival, with all treatments showing high survival rates.

h. Plant Height (cm)

Variety and media significantly influenced cherry tomato plant height at 70 DAT, while their interaction was insignificant (Table 4). Machyo Red was the tallest (200.68 cm), followed by KT Red (197.74 cm), and Red Joy was the shortest (179.18 cm), consistent with findings by Islam et al. (2012) and Kumar (2011). Among media, M₃ produced the tallest plants, followed by M₁, with M₂ yielding the shortest.

Increases in height were observed to be highest at 10 to 20 DAT with an average increase of 18.43cm, followed by 40 to 50 DAT (18.21 cm), and the lowest increase was recorded at 50 to 60 DAT (8.17cm). The poor performance of M₂ with essential sawdust was due to high porosity and low water retention that may not provide enough contact for the roots to facilitate the uptake of nutrients (Nkongho, 2023).

Table 4: Growth parameters of vegetatively propagated cherry tomatoes in the greenhouse

Treatment	Survival Rate (%)	Plant Height (cm)	Days to flower
Varieties			
KT Red	100	197.74 a	22
Machyo Red	98	200.68 a	23
Red Joy	100	179.18 b	23
Growing Media			
M ₁ - 100% coco chips	100	220.77 ab	21 b
M ₂ - 60% sawdust + 40% garden soil	99	112.43 c	28 a
M ₃ - 50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust	100	230.70 a	21 b
M ₄ -30% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 40% rice hull	99	208.46 b	21 b

Different letters represent significant statistical values at (p<0.05).

i. Days to Flower (80% Flowering)

Varieties showed no significant difference in the number of days to flower (Table 4). However, media had a highly significant effect, while variety-media interaction was insignificant. Flowering was longest in M₂ (28 days), followed by M₁, M₃, and M₄ (21 days).

The delayed flowering in M₂, which used hardwood sawdust, was likely due to phytotoxins in the wood (Gruda et al., 2009). While protecting wood from pests and infections, these compounds are toxic to plants. Cherry tomatoes in M₂ showed stunted growth and purplish leaves, symptoms of phosphorus deficiency, which impairs flowering (Syarif, 2013). Additionally, stress from limited water availability in M₂ reduced photosynthesis and reallocated energy from reproduction to survival, further delaying flowering (Zia et al., 2021).

j. Number of Flower per Cluster (at 80% Flowering)

The data on the number of flowers per cluster at 80% flowering (Table 5) showed apparent differences based on variety, growing media, and their interaction. Among the varieties, KT Red had the most flowers, especially in M₃ (22) and M₁ (20). Machyo Red had the fewest flowers, with its best count in M₃ (10 flowers). Red Joy performed moderately, producing its highest flower numbers in M₁ (18 flowers) and M₃ (17 flowers). These results match the findings by Venkadeswaran et al. (2018) and Mohamed et al. (2012), who noted cherry tomato lines can produce 4.2 to 51.2 flowers per cluster. The type of growing media also played a significant role in flower production. M₃ supported the most flowers for all varieties due to its good nutrient supply and water-holding ability. On the other hand, M₂ had the fewest flowers, especially for Machyo Red (4), likely because its high porosity made it hard for plants to retain water and nutrients. The M₁ and M₄ gave average results, with M₁ performing best for KT Red and Red Joy, while M₄ showed balanced results across varieties. This supports Qadir and Ishtiaq (1998), who found that growing media strongly affects flower production.

Table 5: Yield and Yield parameters of vegetatively propagated cherry tomatoes in the greenhouse

Treatment	# of Flower/ cluster	Yield (kg/h)	Brix Value
Varieties			
KT Red	17 a	218.37	8.96 a
Machyo Red	7 c	204.35	7.50 c
Red Joy	14 b	217.41	8.31 b
Growing Media			
M ₁ - 100% coco chips	15ab	218.32 c	8.15
M ₂ - 60% sawdust + 40% garden soil	5 c	12.51 d	8.22
M ₃ - 50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust	17 a	328.80 a	8.18
M ₄ -30% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 40%rice hull	14 b	293.88 b	8.48

Different letters represent significant statistical values at (p<0.05).

k. Yield (kg/house)

The yield of cherry tomatoes (Table 5) showed a highly significant difference based on the growing media. In contrast, no significant effects were observed from the variety or the interaction between variety and media. Among the varieties, KT Red had the highest yield (218.37 kg/h), closely followed by Red Joy (217.41 kg/h), with the lowest yield recorded in Machyo Red (204.35 kg/h). The growing media had a significant impact on yield. M₃ produced the highest yield (328.81 kg/h), followed by M₄ (293.88 kg/h), while M₂ had the lowest yield (12.50 kg/h). The superior performance of M₃ can be attributed to its ability to support a higher number of flowers per cluster, leading to improved fruit sets and overall productivity. This aligns with Rajya Laxmi et al. (2015), who reported that maximum photosynthetic activity and fruit production result from more flowers, which form fruits when sufficient nutrients are available during growth and development.

I. Brix Value

The data showed that the brix value showed a highly significant difference in variety but failed to show significance as influenced by media and interaction of variety and media.

Brix value was observed to be highest in KT Red (8.96), followed by Red Joy (8.31), and lowest in Machyo Red (7.50). Agoston et al. (2017) stated that brix value is highly influenced by the cultivar and its harvest time.

m. Cost and Return Analysis

The cost and return analysis (Table 6) indicates that the M₃ treatment consistently achieves the highest return on cost (ROC) across all three cherry tomato varieties (KT Red, Machyo Red, and Red Joy). This is attributed to its high yields and relatively low production costs. In contrast, M₁ treatments incur higher media costs, resulting in lower ROIs. The M₂ treatments yield poorly, leading to negative ROIs. While M₄ is more cost-efficient than M₁, its ROC remains slightly lower than M₃, though the difference is not statistically significant. Overall, M₃ emerges as the most profitable growing medium for all varieties tested.

Table 6: Cost and return analysis on seeds, nursery, and growing media

Treatments	Yield (kg)	Gross Income	Production Cost	Return on Cost
V ₁ M ₁	229.88	41,378.40	23,794.00	17,584.40
V ₁ M ₂	10.24	1,843.80	5,988.00	-4,144.20
V ₁ M ₃	343.75	61,875.00	8,470.40	53,404.60
V ₁ M ₄	289.61	52,129.20	6,423.20	45,706.00
V ₂ M ₁	217.13	39,084.00	23,794.00	15,290.00
V ₂ M ₂	13.51	2,432.40	5,988.00	-3,555.60
V ₂ M ₃	303.11	54,559.20	8,470.40	46,088.80
V ₂ M ₄	283.64	51,055.20	6,423.20	44,632.00
V ₃ M ₁	207.92	37,425.00	23,794.00	13,631.00
V ₃ M ₂	13.76	2,476.20	5,988.00	-3,511.80
V ₃ M ₃	339.56	61,120.80	8,470.40	52,650.50
V ₃ M ₄	308.39	55,509.60	6,423.20	49,086.40

CONCLUSION

Results revealed that KT Red was the best variety, yielding the highest (218.37 kg/h) and performing consistently well across all media, especially in M₃. The M₃ (50% garden soil + 30% commercial compost + 20% sawdust) was the most effective growing medium, promoting the best growth, flower production, and yield due to its optimal nutrient content and water retention.

In contrast, M₂ (60% sawdust + 40% garden soil) performed poorly, delayed flowering resulting in lower yields. The cost and return analysis showed that M₃ offered the highest ROI, making it the most cost-effective medium. M₂, with low yields, resulted in negative ROIs. Overall, KT Red and M₃ are recommended for maximizing yield and profitability in greenhouse cherry tomato production.

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Declaration of Interest Statement

We, ARLYN T. TIMARIO and MYRNA G. PABIONA, hereby disclose that we have no financial or personal conflicts of interest related to this research. We have no affiliations, financial interests, or personal relationships that could be perceived as influencing the outcome of this study. Our research and findings are conducted with impartiality and integrity, with the sole aim of contributing to advancing knowledge in the field. Any support or funding received for this study has been disclosed in the acknowledgments section of the research.

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